

Ω_Λ

Ryan Jamie Buchanan

August 26, 2024

$$\Omega_\Lambda = \int_X \left(\frac{1}{2} d \left(\int_Y \psi(y_0 + x_0) d(y_0 - x_0) \right) \right) \quad (0.1)$$

We define our “rest” states:

$$y_0 = y_1 - \Delta_i[y_{j-i}] \quad (0.2)$$

$$x_0 = x_1 - \Delta_i[x_{j-i}] \quad (0.3)$$

Define the spaces:

$$X = \bigcup_i^N x_i \quad Y = \bigcup_j^{N+1} y_j \quad (0.4)$$

$$j \in [1, \dots, N+1] > i \in [0, \dots, N] \quad (0.5)$$

Define the spaces of non-resting states:

$$X^* = X \setminus x_0 \quad Y^* = Y \setminus \{y_0, y_{\Delta r+1}\} \quad (0.6)$$

where $r = j - i$.

Define the box product:

$$X^* \times_{\mathcal{Z}(X \times Y)} Y^* = X \boxtimes Y \quad (0.7)$$

and the spectrum:

$$\text{Spec}(X \boxtimes Y) = \text{Spec}(X^*) \cup \text{Spec}(Y^*) \cup \text{Spec}(\mathcal{Z}(X \times Y)) \quad (0.8)$$

where $\mathcal{Z}$ is the partition function.

1 Quantum Well Setup

Let Q be a quantum well; formally, let it consist of maps $\text{Bord}_n \rightarrow \mathcal{H} \times \mathcal{H}$. We form the diagram:

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \text{Bord}_n & \longrightarrow & \mathcal{H} \times \mathcal{H} \\ \uparrow & & \uparrow \\ \text{Spec}(X \boxtimes Y) & \longrightarrow & \text{Frob}_{X, Y, \otimes} \end{array}$$

where $\mathcal{H} \times \mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}^{n-1} \times \mathcal{H}^{n-1}$ are the feet projections from the belt of a cobordism, and where $Frob_{X,Y,\otimes}$ is a Frobenius algebra.

Write

$$\mathcal{H} \times \mathcal{H}|_{Spec(X \boxtimes Y)} = \bigoplus_t Spec(Q_t) \quad (1.1)$$

$$= \Omega \quad (1.2)$$

where $Q \in \{X, Y\}$ and $\oplus$ is the Whitney sum.

Definition 1.1. A structure is defined to be metastable if, for a Wilson line $\mathcal{W}$, we have

$$\int_{\mathcal{W}} \frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial t} \rightarrow 0$$

where

$$\Omega = \int \mathcal{H} \times \mathcal{H} \, d Spec(X \boxtimes Y) \quad (1.3)$$

$$\approx \oint \frac{\partial(j+i)}{\partial(j-i)} \quad (1.4)$$

$$\approx \Omega_{\Lambda} - \Delta Tr(\Lambda) \quad (1.5)$$

Now we define Λ :

$$\Lambda = \begin{bmatrix} y_0 - x_0 & 0 \\ 0 & y_0 + x_0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1.6)$$

We have:

$$\Lambda_{00}\Lambda_{11} = (y_0 - x_0)(y_0 + x_0) \quad (1.7)$$

$$= (y_0)^2 + y_0x_0 - x_0^2 \quad (1.8)$$

$$= (y - x)_0^2 + (yx)_0 \quad (1.9)$$

$$= y \otimes_0^2 x \quad (1.10)$$

1.1 Interpretation

We conceptualize a particle in superposition between N many states as having an $(N + 1)$ -fold cover. With $\mathcal{N} = 2$ supersymmetry, the operator $x \otimes_0^2 y$ roughly characterizes the “disagreement” between interacting fermionic and bosonic fields. This value determines to what degree a string fails to remain at rest with respect to a minimal enclosed neighborhood. A string which minimizes its worldvolume will have a value close to

$$x \otimes_0^2 y = (x \otimes_0^2 y) - f(x \otimes_0^2 y) \quad (1.11)$$

where f is a root of unity for the multiplicative identity.

We can think of Ω_{Λ} as being the eccentricity of an ellipsoidal Poincaré wave. It is quantum flux caused by superposition.

2 PSZ Triangle and Spin Memory

The spin-memory effect/PSZ triangle was discovered by Sabrina Paterski, Andrew Strominger, and Alexander Zhiboedov in [1]. We defined:

$$\Lambda_{PSZ} = \frac{[\Lambda\alpha_{zz} - \Lambda\beta^{uv}, \Lambda\alpha_{zz} - \Lambda\beta^{vu}]}{[\Lambda\alpha^{zz} + \Lambda\beta_{uv}, \Lambda\alpha^{zz} + \Lambda\beta_{vu}]} \quad (2.1)$$

where $\alpha \in X^*$, $\beta \in Y^*$, z is the time channel, and u and v are the spatial channels. zz is referred to as the time-time component in relativity; α_{zz} is the covariant time-time tensor, and α^{zz} the contravariant one.

Let $\rho_{nm} = (p^m(y_0 \mp x_0) \pm \rho_{00})^{m-n}$ where

$$\rho_{00} = \sum_{s=0}^N \underbrace{(y_0 \mp x_0) \pm \dots \pm (y_0 \mp x_0)}_{s \text{ times}}$$

We define the PSZ Green functions by:

$$G(z, \phi) = -\frac{1}{\pi} \sin^2 \frac{\rho_{nm}}{2} \log \sin^2 \frac{\rho_{nm}}{2} \quad , \quad \sin^2 \frac{\rho_{nm}(z, \phi)}{2} \equiv \frac{|z - \phi|^2}{(1 + \phi\bar{\phi})(1 + z\bar{z})} \quad (2.2)$$

where $\phi = u + v$.

Integrating over the initial space we obtain:

$$E\Omega_\Lambda = \int_{X \boxtimes Y} \frac{e^{ik\|(y-x)_2 - (y-x)_1\|}}{\|(y-x)_2 - (y-x)_1\|} (E - G(z, \phi))^{-1} dr \quad (2.3)$$

which gives us the Emmersonian:

$$G(r_1, r_2, E) = \int_{X \boxtimes Y} \frac{e^{ik\|r_1 - r_2\|}}{\|r_1 - r_2\|} (E - U(r))^{-1} dr + \mathcal{C}_{FM} \quad (2.4)$$

where $\mathcal{C}_{FM}$ is the Florès-Monroe correction term:

$$\mathcal{C}_{FM} = \lim_{n \star l \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n^2 - l^2} \quad (2.5)$$

where n and l are plurisubharmonic PDEs:

$$n = n_{\bar{z}t} \quad l = l_{\bar{z}t} \quad (2.6)$$

Finally, we compute $\Omega_{\Lambda_{PSZ}}$ by:

$$G(\omega, G(z, \phi), E) \quad (2.7)$$

where ω is the curvature as defined in [5].

2.1 Bespoke Dual Resonance

To address the issue of spin memory in the context of BDR, we introduce a new vertex operator that incorporates a non-local spin-spin interaction. This vertex operator is defined as follows:

$$V_{spin}(z) = \int d\theta [\psi(z) \otimes \chi(z + \theta) + \psi(z + \theta) \otimes \chi(z)] e^{i\alpha\sigma_z \otimes \sigma_z}$$

where $\psi(z)$ and $\chi(z)$ are fermionic fields, σ_z is the Pauli spin matrix, and α is a coupling constant. This vertex operator describes a process where two fermions interact non-locally through their spins, with the strength of the interaction determined by α .

By including this vertex operator in the S-matrix, we can study the effects of spin-spin interactions on the spin memory effect. We expect that this will lead to new phenomena and potentially modify the existing predictions for spin memory in string theory.

A References

- [1] S.G. Paterski, et al., *New Gravitational Memories*, (2015)
- [2] C. Cheung, G.N. Remmen, *Bespoke Dual Resonance*, (2023)
- [3] P. Emmerson, *Morphic Topology of Numeric Energy: A Fractal Morphism of Topological Counting Shows Real Differentiation of Numeric Energy*, (2023)
- [4] P. Emmerson, *Quantum Mechanics and Energy Numbers*, (2023)
- [5] P. Emmerson, *Infinity Tensors, The Strange Attractor, and the Riemann Hypothesis*, (2023)